

METABOLIC SYNDROME IS A LEADING CAUSE OF CORONARY HEART DISEASE

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The aim of the work. All signs of the metabolic syndrome are risk factors for cardiovascular disease - and their concomitant exacerbates the situation the presence of insulin resistance was only studied. In related individual components of the metabolic syndrome.

Materials and methods. Changes occurring in the metabolic syndrome for a long time occur without any changes, and in particular during adolescence in such diseases diabetes type 2 hypertension and atherosclerotic vascular damage processes develop earlier than the clinic. An early sign of the metabolic syndrome is considered to be dyslipidemia and hypertension. All components of the metabolic syndrome do not occur simultaneously. The manifestations of the metabolic syndrome correlated with phenotype and genotype, as well as the influence of environmental factors on the body. In turn, hyperinsulinemia by means of violation autoregulation of insulin receptors increases peripheral insulin resistance. Also, free fatty acids that block inhibitory insulin property on gluconeogenesis and increased glucose production from the liver. Free fatty acids are in competition with fatty acids from substrates cycle glucose in muscle and glucose utilization block myocytes and this leads to the formation of compensatory hyperinsulinemia and hyperglycemia. Prior to the study, 70 women were examined at the age of 17-49. The study was investigated the presence of bad habits, socio -demographic properties, obstetric history, family history, past illnesses and how they comply with the diet.

Results. Thus the basis of abdominally visceral obesity is the presence of insulin resistance, increased activity of lipoprotein lipase and hepatic triglyceride lipase, reducing the splitting of lipoproteins rich in triglycerides, developing hypertriglyceridemia, and this in turn leads to saturation high triglycerides (HTL) and low density lipoproteins (LDL), raises cholesterol lowering (CL) in the plasma and an increase in fine particles of small, dense low-density lipoprotein (LDL); It was found in the liver excessive input of free fatty acids (FFA), triglycerides and increase the synthesis and secretion of very low density lipoprotein and apolipoprotein.

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Conclusions. Proceeding from the above examination of lipoprotein metabolism disorders occur in conjunction with abdominal visceral obesity leads to early development of coronary heart disease.

